

Computation of Derivative of Geometric Series without Differentiation

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Abstract: This paper presents the computing method for the derivative of geometric series without using the differentiation. This idea will be useful for researchers who are involving in finding the scientific solutions.

MSC Classification codes: 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, geometric series, derivative

Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series.

Summation of geometric series:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n x^i = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^{n-2} + x^{n-1} + x^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x - 1}.$$
$$\sum_{i=k}^n x^i = x^k + x^{k+1} + x^{k+2} + \dots + x^{n-2} + x^{n-1} + x^n = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^k}{x - 1}.$$
$$\sum_{i=-k}^{-1} x^i = x^{-k} + x^{-k+1} + \dots + x^{-2} + x^{-1} = \frac{x^{-1+1} - x^{-k}}{x - 1} = \frac{1 - x^{-k}}{x - 1}.$$

$$\sum_{i=-k}^n x^i = \sum_{i=-k}^{-1} x^i + \sum_{i=0}^n x^i = \frac{1 - x^{-k}}{x - 1} + \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x - 1} = \frac{x^{n+1} - x^{-k}}{x - 1}.$$

First Derivative of Geometric Series

Differentiation is a method of finding the derivative of a function [4-7].

The sum of the geometric series [1 – 5] is that $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i = \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x - 1}$, which is a function of x .

The first derivative of geometric series is computed without using differentiation as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=n-2}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1} x^i$$
$$= \frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x^2}{x - 1} + \dots + \frac{x^n - x^{n-2}}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x^{n-1}}{x - 1}.$$

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=n-2}^{n-1} x^i + \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (i+1)x^i$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x^2}{x - 1} + \dots + \frac{x^n - x^{n-2}}{x - 1} + \frac{x^n - x^{n-1}}{x - 1} &= \frac{nx^n - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^i}{x - 1} \\ &= \frac{nx^n - \left(\frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1}\right)}{x - 1} = \frac{(nx - n - 1)x^n + 1}{(x - 1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,
$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (i+1)x^i = \frac{(nx - n - 1)x^n + 1}{(x - 1)^2}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

Note that
$$\sum_{i=k}^{n-1} (i+1)x^i = \frac{((n-k)x - (n-k) - 1)x^n + x^k}{(x - 1)^2}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

These results denote the first derivative [6-11] of geometric series.

Let us find the derivative of geometric series with negative exponents.

Sum of the geometric series with negative exponents is that
$$\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} = \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1}.$$

The first derivative of geometric series with negative exponents is computed without using differentiation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} &= \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1} \Rightarrow (-x^{-1}) \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} = -x^{-2} - x^{-3} - x^{-4} - \dots - x^{-n-1} = (-x^{-1}) \frac{1 - x^{-n}}{x - 1} \\ \Rightarrow (-) \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i-1} &= -x^{-2} - x^{-3} - x^{-4} - \dots - x^{-n-1} = \frac{-x^{-1} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

Then,
$$\begin{aligned} - \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i-1} - \sum_{i=2}^n x^{-i-1} - \sum_{i=3}^n x^{-i-1} - \dots - \sum_{i=n}^n x^{-i-1} \\ = \frac{-x^{-1} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \frac{-x^{-2} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \frac{-x^{-3} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1} + \dots + \frac{-x^{-n} + x^{-n-1}}{x - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying this expression, we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (-i)x^{-i-1} = \frac{-\sum_{i=1}^n x^{-i} + nx^{-n-1}}{x - 1} = \frac{-(1 - x^{-n})}{x - 1} + nx^{-n-1} = \frac{x^{-n} - 1 + nx^{-n-1}(x - 1)}{(x - 1)^2}.$$

Thus,
$$\sum_{i=1}^n (-i)x^{-i-1} = \frac{((n+1)x - n)x^{-n-1} - 1}{(x - 1)^2}, \quad (x \neq 1).$$

This result denotes the derivative [6-11] of geometric series with negative exponents.

Conclusion

In this article, the derivatives of geometric series are computed without using differentiation. This idea will be useful for researchers who are involving in finding the scientific solutions.

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